

Board Collaboration and Service Delivery in Constitutional Commissions in Kenya

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Abstract:

Constitutional commissions are currently a widely celebrated phenomenon in public governance. Many democracies all over the world, including Kenya have adopted independent constitutional commissions as a system of governance to improve service delivery. Researchers have generally supported the position that board collaboration influences service delivery. The purpose of the study was to establish the influence of board collaboration on service delivery in constitutional commissions in Kenya. The theory was hinged to Stewardship Theory. The study adopted both descriptive

survey and exploratory research designs, and used both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The units of analysis were constitutional commissions of Kenya created by the chapter 15 of the Constitution of Kenya and Act of Parliament. The target population was the 202 (CEOs, head of departments and board members) in the constitutional commissions in Kenya. The data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Results revealed that board collaboration had a positive and significant relationship with service delivery in the constitutional commissions in Kenya. The study implies that fostering effective board collaboration is crucial for enhancing service delivery in Kenya's constitutional commissions, suggesting a strategic focus on collaborative governance practices.

Keywords: *Board Collaboration, Service delivery.*

Introduction

Many democracies, including Kenya, have adopted independent constitutional commissions as a governance system to enhance service delivery, with board collaboration playing a crucial role in this process. Researchers generally support the view that board governance, including collaborative practices, influences service delivery (Conforth, 2020;

Solomon, 2020). However, existing research predominantly focuses on developed or developing countries in Asia and Latin America (Namuhisa, 2020; Moursli, 2020; Hodginkson et al., 2017; Nyagilo & Njeru, 2020; Schalka & Sarfati, 2014; Kosec & Wantchenkon, 2020), and the relationship between board collaboration and service delivery in the context of constitutional commissions in Sub-Saharan Africa is scarcely explored.

Board governance, including collaborative efforts, is rooted in the political economy argument that it leads to better service delivery (Oslo, 2018). Despite these theoretical foundations advocating for effective board collaboration, findings on its impact on service delivery in the public sector are mixed and inconclusive. While some studies suggest that board governance and collaboration lead to improved service delivery (Park, 2020; Solomon, 2020), other research indicates that aspects of corporate governance, including collaboration, can negatively influence service delivery (Moursli, 2020; Schalka & Sarfati, 2014; Kosec & Wantchenkon, 2020). These mixed conclusions highlight the need for research focusing on the Kenyan context to establish the effect of board collaboration and governance on service delivery in Kenya's constitutional commissions

Statement of the Problem

The 2010 Constitution of Kenya established independent Constitutional Commissions to enhance service delivery; however, the transition has faced numerous challenges, including turf wars, corruption, and strikes. Statistics reveal significant public dissatisfaction, with the 2017 KIPPRA report highlighting severe service delivery issues, Transparency International (2018) reporting 41% dissatisfaction, and Amnesty International (2018) finding that 45% of respondents had negative feedback. Additionally, the 2017 ACAL survey revealed a 66% dissatisfaction rate concerning equity, dignity, and service delivery efficiency, alongside issues with technology use and accessibility.

While existing studies, such as those by Maina, Namusonge, and Kabare (2016) and Koitie (2015), have explored various aspects of service delivery in constitutional commissions, there remains a notable gap in understanding the role of board collaboration. The current research aims to address this void by examining how board collaboration impacts service delivery within Kenya's constitutional commissions, filling gaps left by previous studies and contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of effective governance practices in this context.

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between board collaboration and service delivery in constitutional commissions in Kenya.

Literature Review

The study utilizes stewardship theory, originating from Sociology and Psychology, to examine board collaboration within constitutional commissions in Kenya. Unlike Agency theory, which emphasizes the need for monitoring and control, Stewardship theory posits that managers act as stewards who protect and maximize the owner's wealth, thus aligning their interests with the organization's success (Kabiru, Theuri, & Misiko, 2018; Makori & Kinyua, 2019). This theory suggests that managers are inherently motivated to enhance organizational performance, leading to minimized agency costs and a more trust-based decision-making environment (Mabati, Onserio, Mutai, & Bii, 2020; Solomon, 2020).

In the context of board collaboration, Stewardship theory emphasizes the importance of trust and insider knowledge in enhancing board effectiveness and service delivery (Mok, Chan, & Wen, 2020). It argues that effective board collaboration can mitigate the negative impacts of power separation and enhance service delivery by fostering a collaborative and well-informed management team (Minjire & Ogollah, 2017; Nyagilo & Njeru, 2020). Furthermore, while board independence may offer monitoring incentives, it can also hinder managerial initiative (Muchai, Makokha & Namusonge, 2018). Thus, Stewardship theory supports the notion that collaborative board dynamics, informed by trust and shared goals, are crucial for optimizing service delivery within Kenya's constitutional commissions (Kande, Namusonge, & Mugambi, 2017; Maroa & Namusonge, 2019).

Conceptual Model and Hypothesis

Conceptual framework can be defined as a set of broad ideas and principles taken from relevant fields of inquiry and used to structure a

subsequent presentation (Myers, 2013). The current study hypothesizes that board collaboration linearly and directly influences service delivery of constitutional commissions in Kenya. The independent variable is board collaboration. The dependent variable is service

delivery in the constitutional commissions of Kenya. Service delivery is conceptualized as accessibility of services, efficiency of services, quality of services and citizen satisfaction (complements and complaints) in to the services in the constitutional commissions In Kenya.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Empirical Review

Board collaboration involves the cooperative interaction and collective decision-making among board members, leveraging their diverse perspectives and expertise to achieve organizational goals. In the context of constitutional commissions in Kenya, effective board collaboration is essential for improving service delivery, as it integrates varied viewpoints and expertise to address complex governance and service challenges. The increasing emphasis on board collaboration encompassing different demographic and cognitive dimensions can significantly enhance collaborative efforts by introducing a broader range of perspectives and problem-solving approaches (Manyaga, Muturi & Oluoch, 2020). This collaboration can lead to more innovative solutions and better decision-making, ultimately improving the efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery within constitutional commissions.

However, board collaboration can also face challenges, particularly when managing diverse teams. While collaboration brings valuable insights and enhances decision-making, it can also introduce potential conflicts and communication barriers that may impede

collaboration (Omware, Atheru, & Jagongo, 2020). The mixed results in studies on board collaboration and performance highlight the need for effective management of these collaborative processes. For instance, while ethnic collaboration has been shown to positively influence performance, general collaboration effects are less consistent (Nyangilo & Njeru, 2020). This underscores the importance of not only fostering collaboration but also implementing robust mechanisms for facilitating effective board collaboration. Addressing these challenges through targeted strategies and policies can enhance the collaborative capacity of boards, thereby improving service delivery and overall performance of constitutional commissions in Kenya.

Research Methodology

The target population for the study was all the constitutional commissions in Kenya as established in Constitution of Kenya (2010). The target population was the 202 (CEOs, Head of departments and Board members) in the constitutional commissions. The study adopted a census with respect of unit of observation and

therefore ruled out application of any specific sampling technique. The study used a census since the population of 202 is small which less than 250 and the study aimed to reach all the respondents. The census approach is justified since according to Kinai and Were (2017) data gathered using census contributes towards gathering of unbiased data representing all individuals' opinions on a study problem (Kihara, Bwisa, & Kihoro, 2016). The study collected views from the respondents because they are involved in implementation of all aspects of board collaboration in the constitutional commissions and are seen to be information rich for the purpose of this study.

Results and Discussion

The Pearson correlation analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between board collaboration (BC) and service delivery (SD) in the constitutional commissions of Kenya. Specifically, the correlation coefficient of 0.555 indicates a moderate to strong positive association, with a p-value of 0.000 confirming statistical significance. This suggests that as the level of board collaboration increases, so does the effectiveness of service delivery within these commissions.

The positive correlation underscores the critical role of board collaboration in improving service delivery. Collaborative boards benefit from diverse perspectives and collective expertise, which enhances decision-making and problem-solving capabilities. This, in turn, leads to more effective and efficient service delivery. The significant correlation suggests that fostering a collaborative environment among board members can substantially improve service outcomes, ensuring that constitutional commissions operate more effectively and meet their service delivery goals. The positive correlation underscores the critical role of board collaboration in enhancing service delivery. Collaborative boards leverage diverse perspectives and collective expertise, which significantly improve decision-making and

problem-solving capabilities. This alignment is consistent with previous studies highlighting that effective collaboration within boards leads to better organizational outcomes. For instance, studies by Sánchez-Teba, Benítez-Márquez, and Porrás-Alcalá (2021) emphasize that increased board collaboration and collaboration positively affect organizational performance by improving decision-making processes. Similarly, a study by Waweru, Mangena, and Riro (2019) demonstrated that the dynamics within a well-collaborative board structure enhance firm performance

The significance of the correlation ($p=0.000$) allows us to reject the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no relationship between board collaboration and service delivery. Given the strong statistical significance, it is evident that board collaboration does indeed have a meaningful impact on service delivery. This rejection of the null hypothesis reinforces the notion that enhancing collaborative practices among board members is crucial for improving service delivery in constitutional commissions. The findings provide empirical support for the importance of board collaboration in achieving better organizational performance and more effective service outcomes. For example, Nyagilo and Njeru (2020) found that board collaboration and collaboration were linked to improved performance in various contexts, indicating that these factors contribute positively to service delivery. Furthermore, research by Solomon (2020) suggests that board collaboration, a facet of effective governance, leads to enhanced service delivery in both public and private sector organizations. The findings from the current study corroborate these earlier conclusions by providing empirical evidence that board collaboration significantly impacts service delivery in constitutional commissions. Thus, enhancing collaborative practices within boards can lead to substantial improvements in service outcomes, aligning with the broader literature on effective governance and organizational performance

Table 1. Correlation Matrix for Board Collaboration and Service Delivery

		BC	SD
Board Collaboration	Pearson Correlation	.1*	
	Sig.(2-tailed)		
	N		
	N		
Service Delivery	Pearson Correlation	.555**	.1*
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000	
	N	186	
	N		

Note: *. Correlation is only significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed); SD = Service Delivery, BC= Board Collaboration

Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis indicates a significant positive relationship between board collaboration and service delivery in Kenya's constitutional commissions, validating the rejection of the null hypothesis. This finding suggests that enhanced board collaboration directly contributes to improved service delivery outcomes. The results align with prior research highlighting that effective board collaboration and diverse perspectives can lead to better decision-making and organizational performance. Therefore, fostering a collaborative environment within boards is essential for enhancing service quality and efficiency in constitutional commissions. Therefore, to enhance service delivery in Kenya's constitutional commissions, it is crucial to foster effective board collaboration through structured processes and regular strategic meetings. Promoting board collaboration by integrating varied expertise, gender, and backgrounds can enrich decision-making and address public needs more comprehensively. Additionally, implementing robust communication channels, providing targeted board training, and regularly evaluating collaboration practices will further improve governance and service outcomes

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